

A Systematic Literature Review on Work-Life Balance with a Particular Focus on Working Women

Altina Avdullahi ¹

¹ ELTE University, Budapest, 1075, Hungary

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Abstract

This systematic literature review explores work-life balance (WLB) with an emphasis on how it affects working mothers and women, as well as organizational performance. Initially ten articles were selected from the Web of Science database, published between 2014 and 2024, and then three additional studies were added to increase the number of the quantitative and case studies. This sample of research studies was analyzed using the PRISMA 2020 guidelines. The results emphasize the difficulties women encounter when balancing work and domestic obligations, such as role conflict, stress, and limited career advancement. It has been demonstrated that good work-life balance practices, such as flexible scheduling, encouraging company culture, and family-friendly policies, improve employee satisfaction, productivity, and employee loyalty. However, progress towards gender equality in WLB is still hampered by enduring cultural norms and workplace expectations. The review emphasizes how companies and legislators can work together to create environments that support women's needs and promote organizational performance.

Keywords

work-life balance, PRISMA, working women, employee well-being, organizational performance, flexible work arrangements, gender equality, workplace policies

JEL codes: I31, J24, J28, O25

Introduction

Nowadays, the demands set by the labor market usually include long working hours, continuous evaluation of performance through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and targets that employees are expected to meet. On the other hand, balancing work and

family with the allure of various opportunities for travel, sports activities, and leisure entertainment poses challenges for the workforce. Individuals often find themselves in situations where they must determine their priorities, leading to dilemmas regarding what is more important and deserves priority. According to Clark's (2000) definition, pleasure and functioning at work and home are linked with minimal role conflict. Thus, for many people, finding a good balance between a personal and work life has become more difficult in modern fast-paced society. The situation is even more complicated for women, especially for mothers who strive to be good parents while also performing well at work, often sacrificing leisure time and social activities. Achieving a balance between personal and work responsibilities is known as work-life balance or WLB (Moses 2020). This includes managing one's time, managing stress, and increasing the overall happiness. In the public debate, the term "work-life balance" has become more and more frequent (Kelliher et al. 2019). It offers a new ethical framework for the workplace that developed countries and public and private companies around the world are pursuing. Professionals in human service institutions are frequently obliged to spend most of their time working closely with others (Maslach & Jackson 1981). This definition posits that work and home life have a mutual impact on domestic and organizational identities (Emslie & Hunt 2009; Medina et al. 2023).

This study aims to provide an overview of WLB in today's dynamic world, focusing exclusively on the impact of WLB on organization performance and employees with a particular focus on working women and mothers. Additionally, it aims to summarize the most effective strategies and interventions for promoting WLB in contemporary work environments, as evidenced by the systematic literature review.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework derives from the literature on main theories on work-life balance and its impact on the performance of organizations and employees, with a particular focus on working women as well as effective strategies and interventions for promoting WLB in contemporary work environments.

Work-Life Balance (WLB)

WLB has been conceptualized and examined from a variety of theoretical perspectives, providing unique insights into the topic.

Evolution of approaches to work-life balance in scientific literature

At first, it was thought that life and work were two distinct domains that are not related to each other. The authors of the segmentation theory Blood and Wolfe (1960), highlighted that the division of work and home is a common process for employees who are dissatisfied, underperforming, or have uninteresting employment. According to this theory, personal and professional lives are distinct and autonomous (ibid.). This implies that experiences at work, such as stress or satisfaction, do not necessarily carry over into personal life, and vice versa. As a result, one domain can become disconnected from the other, which naturally helps restore work-life balance (ibid.).

According to the Compensation theory, people try to make up for their dissatisfaction in one area (job or family) by becoming more involved or looking for rewards in the other area (Piotrkowski 1979). According to Piotrkowski (ibid.), employees look to their homes as havens, and look to their families as sources of satisfaction lacking in the occupational sphere. According to Kossek and Lambert's (2005) discussion about the Integration theory, work and personal life can be purposefully combined or integrated rather than being kept apart. This method recognizes the reality of contemporary living, where organizational, cultural, and technical advancements have made it harder to draw clear lines between work and non-work (ibid.). The core of the Spillover theory is discussed in Piotrkowski's work (1979), which examines how feelings, attitudes, and behaviors developed in one area (job or family) transfer into the other (Piotrkowski 1979; Piotrkowski & Crits-Christoph 1981).

Research on the interaction between work and family has shifted away from work-family enrichment and conflict towards WLB (Greenhaus et al. 2006; Greenhaus & Allen 2011; Wayne et al. 2017; Moazami-Goodarzi et al. 2019). The work-life study has shifted from focusing primarily on the negative aspects of work-life conflict to investigating the beneficial interplay between work, family, and other life roles and the concept of WLB (Jones et al. 2006). Recent demographic and workplace changes, including more women in the workforce, longer working hours, and advanced communication technologies, have made it more important for employees to balance home and work life (Beauregard & Lesley 2009). The Role theory proposes people play numerous life roles, such as an employee, husband, parent, and community member, and that a role conflict occurs when the demands of these roles are contrary (Kalliath & Brough 2008). This concept emphasizes the significance of defining clear boundaries between work and out-of-work concerns to reduce conflicts and improve well-being. The Boundary theory is based on the sociological research of Nippert-Eng (1996), which explores how people find meaning in work and home in order to facilitate the transition. Over the last decades, the significance of managing an employee's WLB has grown considerably (De Bruin & Dupuis 2004).

The impact of WLB on organizational performance

According to Beauregard & Lesley (2009), research on the impact of WLB good practices (also known as policies that are supportive or friendly to family) on organizations is scarce despite the growing interest in the topic among academics and practitioners. In response to frequently conflicting roles in lives, such as an employee, spouse, parent, and community member, employers are under growing pressure to provide at-work policies that support workers in meeting their personal and professional obligations (Rapoport et al. 2002). To create distinct components for internal labor markets where the expectations of the employer and the employee are increasingly different, Atkinson and Meager (1986) proposed the acknowledged model of a "flexible firm". This model envisions the division of the workforce into two categories: full-time, permanent staff and those on the periphery, with the aim to increase the efficiency of enterprises.

Organizational practices have evolved into the "ideal worker", who is foreseen to be male, without external duties, and at the pinnacle of his profession (Bailyn & Harrington 2004). "The ideal worker" stereotype is foreseen to overwork and travel often for the company's needs. Kuroda and Yamamoto (2019) describe overwork as working excessively long hours,

which might negatively affect mental health. Avdullahi & Yildirim (2021) showed that the emotional stability of individuals has a substantial effect on the link between emotion regulation and overwork.

In reality, the workforce includes more older workers and women, as well as a large number of moms with children younger than five years (Bailyn & Harrington 2004). Companies have devised diverse family-friendly flexible work arrangements, including compressed workweeks, flexible daily schedules, maternity leave with part-time options upon return, remote work, and allowances for family-related absences. Ca-been (2023) points out that healthy leaders can control their wellness and priorities but also instill motivation, confidence, great collaboration, and passion in their teams and stakeholders.

The impact of WLB on employees, with a particular focus on working women

Work organizations are rapidly changing, necessitating a dynamic approach to addressing the issues of occupational health and safety (Titopoulou et al. 2017). According to Avdullahi and Yildirim (2021), today's industrial working environment has been compelled to lengthen employee working hours, which has an impact on their moods. Employees consequently do not have enough time for "quality family time" (Jenkins & Harvey 2019), and families are particularly impacted. Low physical, psychological, and emotional well-being is caused by significant demands on time consumed by both family and work (Jensen & Knudsen 2017).

The roles of working women have evolved globally in response to economic and social forces (Delina & Raya 2013). Women's position as housekeepers has not been debilitated. Therefore, women in the workforce have the twin roles of a working woman and homemaker (Zhang et al. 2020). Due to this, working women are now facing tremendous pressure to excel their careers on par their male counterparts, while also maintaining their family responsibilities (Lakshmi & Prasanth 2018). Based on the Boundary theory, people can deliberately build and keep integrated or segmented boundaries between spheres of work and family (Ashforth et al. 2000; Xie et al. 2022). Pan & Sun (2022) interviewed twenty professional women in semi-structured interviews, and their findings show that the most difficult aspect of their lives was the reliance of their children on them.

Creating a clear border between work and family can result in negative employee effects, such as low family satisfaction and emotional tiredness (Xie et al. 2022; Pan & Sun 2022). A group of four authors found that depression symptoms among single mothers are caused by low-wage jobs and financial strain, which might influence their parenting skills and, subsequently, their children's behavior (Jackson et al. 2000). Pan & Sun (2022), found that time management and silence are two of the most well-known factors influencing women's WLB. Policies promoting WLB have been criticized for failing to produce "gender-neutral" or harmonious work and family practices (Burnett et al. 2010). Part of the reason for this is that societal shifts about the paternal role are not taken into account by organizational expectations (Burnett et al. 2010).

Women faced an impenetrable steel ceiling and still under the paternalistic work culture, they face a glass ceiling in today's competitive neoliberal workplace (Brumley 2014). When starting and running businesses, women trail their male counterparts

(Avdullahi & Ademi 2020). Cooke (2023), based on the literature review, found that things can be improved through efforts made by women to better themselves, support from families and organizations, and improved institutional procedures to open up management job paths for women. Women who fit the ideal may be able to break through the ceiling and reach higher levels (Brumley 2014). Professional women regard time management as the main aspect of getting a better WLB and enhancing their subject awareness and resilience, which will give them more influence over their jobs and lives (Pan & Sun 2022). According to Burnett et al. (2010), mothers are more likely to work flexibly when it comes to the adoption of WLB policies aimed at “generalized” working population.

Effective strategies and interventions for promoting WLB in contemporary work environments

Work-life programs were introduced before the Second World War, as the W.K. Kellogg Company replaced the standard three daily eight-hour hours with four six-hour shifts, which enhanced staff morale and efficiency (Lockwood 2003). Finding a good WLB is a global challenge that all professionals face. The well-being of all family members depends mainly on the ability to successfully balance jobs, family responsibilities, and personal life. By analyzing work schedule optimization in the 21st century, Titopoulou et al. (2017) concluded that while considering public needs, it is critical to establish an equilibrium between workers’ needs for occupational health and safety, personal/family life, and enterprise requirements.

Governments can help solve the issue by providing supportive and flexible work policies, allowing parents to strike a better WLB (OECD 2025). Hutchinson (2017) suggests the concept of WLB in the workplace and proposes broadening the “one-size-fits-all” policy toward a more individualized approach.

Remote, a global HR platform, analyzed 60 countries with the highest GDP in the world to determine the ones with the best WLB. They did this by looking at several workplace-related variables, including statutory annual leave, maternity leave, healthcare, sick pay, and overall happiness. Their findings, as shown in Table 1, indicate that New Zealand stands out as the leader among the other ten highly ranked countries in terms of WLB in 2023, with an overall index score of 79.35, which places it at the top. New Zealand was followed by Spain, France, Denmark, Australia, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, Canada, and Brazil (Remote 2024). Remote’s (2024) findings demonstrate that, in addition to a high rate of sick pay (80%), New Zealand provides a government-funded universal healthcare system and an adequate statutory annual leave allotment of 32 days.

Figure 1 shows the OECD country rankings for work-life balance. Italy (with an index of 9.4) is the highest-ranked country in terms of work-life balance (OECD, 2025). In the Top-10, Italy is followed by Denmark (8.6), Norway (8.5), Spain (8.4), the Netherlands (8.3), France and Sweden (both with an index of 8.1), Germany (8.0), the Russian Federation (7.8), Belgium, Lithuania, and Switzerland placed ninth (with an index of 7.7), and Hungary in tenth place (with an index of 7.6) (OECD, 2025).

When these rankings are compared with those provided by Remote, we see that New Zealand, which tops the Remote list with a score of 79 out of 100, has a score index of only 4.9 out of 10 in the OECD ranking. By comparing these rankings, we notice that

all countries that follow New Zealand on the Remote list are ranked higher than New Zealand in the OECD ranking, with Australia being the only exception with a score index of 4.4. In addition, it can be noted that Italy is not among the top countries on the Remote’s list, suggesting a different set of evaluation metrics. Both rankings have countries such as Denmark, Spain, France, and the Netherlands near the top, indicating that they perform well across a range of WLB indicators, regardless of the evaluator’s perspective.

Table 1. Top-10 countries with the best WLB

Overall ranking	Country & Capital city	2023 Country Population	Index score / 100
1	New Zealand , Wellington	5.215.233	79.35
2	Spain , Madrid	47.533.487	75.55
3	France , Paris	64.716.988	75.34
4	Australia , Canberra	26.356.950	73.71
5	Denmark , Copenhagen	5.902.005	73.67
6	Norway , Oslo	5.461.492	73.05
7	Netherlands , Amsterdam	17.601.472	69.14
8	United Kingdom , London	67.665.529	69.07
9	Canada , Ottawa	38.678.341	67.91
10	Brazil , Brasilia	216.033.416	67.73

Source: Remote 2024

Figure 1. Ranking of countries based on Work-Life Balance. Source: OECD 2025

The OECD index takes into account several factors, including the quality of social support networks, leisure time, and actual hours worked (OECD, 2025), whereas Remote considers healthcare systems, maternity leave, sick pay, statutory leave, and general happiness (Remote 2024). Understanding the standards used to evaluate work-life balance is crucial,

as evidenced by the discrepancy between the Remote's and OECD rankings. While OECD appears to evaluate practical results like time utilization and societal balance, Remote places more emphasis on law and policy-driven issues.

Research Aim and Research Questions

The aim of this study is to review and synthesize literature published in the Web of Science, the most widely used database, in terms of WLB impact on organizational performance and employees, with a particular focus on working women, as well as effective strategies and interventions for promoting WLB. To meet the research purpose of this study, the following research questions are constructed:

- How has the term “work-life balance” been discussed in scientific literature in terms of its impact on organizational performance and employees, with a particular focus on working women?
- What are the effective strategies and interventions, recommended by scientific literature, for promoting WLB in contemporary work environments?

Methodology

To identify appropriate papers on work-life balance and its impact on the organizational performance and employees with a particular focus on working women as well as effective strategies and interventions for promoting WLB in contemporary work environments, the author used a systematic approach for the study selection. In addition, the Prisma 2020 standards and recommendations (Page et al. 2021) provided basis for the systematic literature review.

Search Strategy

To meet the research purpose of this study, the author decided to use Web of Science Core Collection database, which is recognized as the most reliable database (Ding, Rousseau & Wolfram 2014).

The author conducted searches using terms All fields (“Work-life balance*” OR “Quality of work life*” OR “Work-life policies*” OR “Work-life balance of Working women*” OR “Working mothers*”) in Web of Science Core Collection database, and received 5.883 results. By setting the year range of 2010–2024 in the English language, 3.156 results were found. By selecting review articles in the English language and in the research areas of Management, Business, Psychology Applied, Psychology Multidisciplinary, Women Studies, Psychology, Economics, Business Finance, and Psychology Social, 87 results were received.

Then the author excluded papers that weren't relevant by screening articles through their abstracts and titles, therefore, 14 studies remained. After assessing for eligibility, four studies were excluded, and 10 studies remained. To increase the number of quantitative and case studies, three studies were included: one study in the Russian Language, indexed in Web of Science, one master's thesis in Spanish, and one case study in the English language, bringing the total number of studies to 13 that were included in the systematic literature review. The search protocol consisted of four steps documented in the adapted PRISMA flow diagram shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Paper collection flow strategy. *Source:* adapted from PRISMA 2020 (Page, et al., 2021)

Results

A content analysis of the final sample of 13 papers has been conducted. The following components were exported in Microsoft Excel for every article in the sample: (1) author(s), (2) year of publication, (3) title, (4) research type, (5) research methodology, and (6) main findings as presented in Table 2. This process gave us a general understanding of how literature has evolved and changed over time, and it also helped us generate descriptive statistics.

The sample included 13 articles published between 2014 and 2024. Figure 3 shows the distribution of the articles by year. The highest number of studies in the sample was published in 2020 (three studies), followed by 2023 (two studies). Additionally, one study was published in each of the years 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2021, and 2024. No studies published in 2022 were included in the sample.

Out of 13 studies included in the sample, 8 were qualitative studies (literature reviews), whereas four were quantitative studies (three studies were survey-type; two were conducted by structural equation modeling, and one was a descriptive, cross-sectional, non-experimental study). One was a qualitative case study, with 20 semi-structured interviews with female engineers.

Based on our systematic literature review, the author answers the research questions of this study. Let's start from the first research question concerning the impact of WLB on organizational performance and employees, focusing on working women. According to Chaudhuri et al. (2020), the work-life research will continue to grow due to the declining social support from extended families and the growing number of dual-earner couples. Executive women stay healthier, more focused, and more productive at work when they are able to strike a balance between work and personal life (Inzúa, Vargas, Santa Cruz & Rodrigo 2016). In addition, Torres et al. (2024) have identified numerous obstacles to leadership and job advancement as a consequence of the parental duties. However, Torres et al. (ibid.) also found that there are benefits to the association between motherhood and professional success, mainly associated with moms becoming more adept at problem-solving, time management, and interpersonal interactions (ibid.).

According to Haar et al. (2014), gender egalitarianism (GE) is a reflection of “societal beliefs about whether members’ roles in their homes, workplaces, and communities should be determined by their biological sex”. Beliefs in the conventional gendered division of labor, which portrays men as the breadwinners and women as the caregivers and housewives, are characteristics of low GE cultures, whereas in high GE cultures the opposite mindset prevails (ibid.). For women to succeed in their careers and life in general, social support – especially from family – is essential (Agarwal 2015). A lack of organizational support, such as remote work or no flexible scheduling, causes employee unhappiness, which can raise turnover and reduce productivity (Inzúa et al. 2016). According to Podolskaya (2019), a lack of WLB policies (and the presence of the glass ceiling) harms a firm’s reputation and inhibits the advancement of bright women, which can disserve innovation and organizational performance. In addition, she stresses that without WLB, women face obstacles to leadership, career discontent, and emotional tiredness (ibid.). Women with low WLB who work long hours experience psychological and physical stress, such as irritation and weariness (Rangarajan, 2018). Inzúa et al. (2016) suggests that firms need to create better WLB policies as they may see an increase in employee loyalty and retention, which would enhance the overall organizational performance.

Table 2. Overview of all articles included in the systematic literature review

Author(s)	Year	Title	Research type	Research methodology	Main Findings
Torres AJC, Barbosa-Silva L, Oliveira-Silva LC, Miziara OPP, Guahy UCR, Fisher AN, Ryan MK	2024	The Impact of Motherhood on Women's Career Progression: A Scoping Review of Evidence-Based Interventions	Qualitative	Organizing and analyzing available literature	Motherhood has positive and negative impacts on career progression, influencing attitudes, behaviors, and relationships at work.
Singh R, Aggarwal S, Sahni S	2023	A Systematic Literature Review of Work-Life Balance Using ADO Model	Qualitative	Organizing and analyzing available literature	Personal, household and organizational factors influence WLB
Srinivasaiah R, Renuka SD, Nanjundeswaraswamy TS	2023	Quality management practices and quality of work life – a conceptual model development	Qualitative	Organizing and analyzing available literature	Research on the connection between quality management practices (QMP) and quality of work life (QWL) is lacking, which emphasizes the need for a more comprehensive strategy to look at how QMP affects workers.
Fan YY, Potocnik K, Chaudhry S	2021	A process-oriented, multilevel, multidimensional conceptual framework of work-life balance support: A multidisciplinary systematic literature review and future research agenda	Qualitative	Organizing and analyzing available literature	The work-life balance is influenced by both personal management and external stressors and support mechanisms within multilevel social systems.
Tijani B, Osei-Kyei R, Feng YB	2020	A review of work-life balance in the construction industry	Qualitative	Organizing and analyzing available literature	Main causes are identified for poor WLB, and WLB initiatives and interventions in developed as well as developing countries

Author(s)	Year	Title	Research type	Research methodology	Main Findings
Chaudhuri S, Arora R, Roy P	2020	Work-Life balance policies and organisational outcomes – a re-view of literature from the Indian context	Qualitative	Organizing and analyzing available literature	WLB regulations have benefited many industries in India, the banking and higher education sectors have adopted employee-friendly WLB policies.
Weale V, Oakman J, Wells Y	2020	Can organisational work-life policies improve work-life interaction? A scoping review	Qualitative	Organizing and analyzing available literature	A friendly work-family culture should be incorporated into organizational policy to assist employees in modifying their work schedules and WLB.
Wood J, Oh J, Park J, Kim W	2020	The Relationship Between Work Engagement and Work- Life Balance in Organizations: A Review of the Empirical Research	Qualitative	Organizing and analyzing available literature	Numerous moderators, mediators, and antecedents demonstrate the connections between WLB and work engagement.
Podolskaya AA	2019	Perceptions of work-life balance by women working in STEM industries (A rocket-and-space industry case study)	Qualitative	20 semi-structured interviews with female engineers	Perceived glass ceilings and gender hurdles underscore the urgent need for organizational reforms to better support women's professions and family lives, while corporate rules, partner involvement, and managerial support all influence work-life balance for women.
Rangarajan R	2018	A Study on Work-Life Balance of Working Women – With Special reference Chennai City	Quantitative	Questionnaire type, One-Way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) Correlation analysis Chi-square tests	Chennai working women, particularly those who are married and have long work hours, struggle greatly to balance work and family life, and the help of their employers is generally insufficient.

Author(s)	Year	Title	Research type	Research methodology	Main Findings
Inzúa RA, Vargas MAL, Santa Cruz TEM, Rodrigo JAR	2016	Balance vida-trabajo de las mujeres ejecutivas que trabajan en empresas privadas en Lima Metropolitana	Quantitative	Survey type, descriptive, cross-sectional, non-experimental study	Organizational policies lag; stronger formal assistance is required to sustain executive women's well-being over the long term, even if many of them can balance their personal lives, careers, and families.
Direnzo MS, Greenhaus JH, Weer CH	2015	Relationship between protean career orientation and work-life balance: A resource perspective	Quantitative	Survey-typed, and structural equation modeling	WLB is positively impacted by protean career orientation (PCO), and this link is mediated by social capital, psychological capital, and perceived employability through career planning and career capital accumulation.
Haar JMH, Russo M, Suñec A, Ollier-Malaterre A	2014	Outcomes of work-life balance on job satisfaction, life satisfaction and mental health: A study across seven cultures	Quantitative	Survey-typed, and structural equation modeling	The study finds that WLB is positively related to job and life satisfaction and negatively related to anxiety and depression across seven cultures, with individualism/collectivism and gender egalitarianism moderating these relationships.

Figure 3. Study distribution by year of publication. *Source:* prepared by the author

Tijani et al. (2020) stresses that proactive steps to reduce or eradicate the causes of poor WLB that lead to family dysfunctions are known as WLB interventions. For example, flexibility in the workplace has a positive impact on workers as it decreases the issue of work-family imbalance among construction workers in industrialized nations, including the U.S., UK, New Zealand, and Australia (Tijani et al. 2020).

Proper WLB policies result in a win-win situation for employees and the firms. WLF policies have played a critical role in improving workers’ life satisfaction, work satisfaction, organizational commitment, and higher organizational performance (Chaudhuri et al. 2020). Women can advance professionally in supportive work environments without compromising their personal lives (Podolskaya 2019). In addition, Chaudhuri et al. (2020), found that supportive work-life policies adopted by Indian organizations led to improvements in well-being, job satisfaction, performance and productivity, loyalty, and dedication, as well as improved citizenship within the organization. Women are more engaged and advanced in their careers at companies with family-friendly policies and managerial support (Podolskaya 2019). Executive women who successfully combine work and life report greater physical health, healthier family ties, and emotional well-being (Inzúa et al. 2016).

In addition, based on the systematic review of the selected sample of relevant literature, we aim to answer the second research question regarding the identification of effective strategies and interventions for promoting WLB in contemporary work environments according to scientific literature. Employees are the most valuable asset to the firm. When workers are not viewed as primary resources, the workforce is considered unsustainable. Employees may be used to further the financial objectives of their employers by exhausting their abilities, talents, and energy, as well as by establishing a supportive and nurturing work environment for their welfare (Singh et al. 2023). Firms search for quality assurance and improvements by establishing good quality management practices. Employees’ Quality of Life-balance

(QWL) is positively correlated with the Quality Management Practices (QMP) (Srinivasiah et al. 2023). According to Inzúa et al. (2016), businesses that provide flexibility and other family-friendly advantages assist women in striking a better balance between their personal and professional lives. Important interventions are a must for fostering work-life balance, including an inclusive culture, explicit policies, and supportive leadership, particularly for women in demanding fields (Podolskaya 2019). In addition, Rangarajan (2018) points out that introducing remote work, flexible scheduling, and stress-reduction initiatives can greatly enhance work-life balance among working women.

Wood et al. (2020) in their research found a variety of moderating (such as preventive coping and work-life imbalance) and mediating (such as family and work demands, supportive work-family culture, and work-family enrichment) factors that have an impact on the relationship between WLB and its related terms and work engagement, particularly the ripple effect of employee turnover. Organizations aim to become flexible with their employees. Weale, Oakman & Wells (2020) emphasize how crucial it is to make sure that organizational policies are complex and ingrained in a work-family culture that encourages employees to use them to change their work schedules and the way they interact with their families. In addition, Direnzo et al. (2015), in their research on a sample of 367 college-educated employees, found that protean career orientation (PCO) was positively related to work-life balance.

Conclusion

According to the results of this comprehensive literature review, work-life balance (WLB) is crucial in the quickly changing labor market of today. Due to the established societal expectations and the demand for playing two roles, women, mothers, in particular, continue to experience challenges in juggling both their private and professional responsibilities. These difficulties frequently cause a great deal of stress, which has an impact on their general well-being, professional advancement, and mental health. The data repeatedly demonstrate that companies are essential in tackling these issues by creating and enforcing flexible work schedules, supportive workplace cultures, and family-friendly policies.

WLB initiatives benefit not only employees but also the organization. Effective WLB policies have been shown to improve organizational commitment, productivity, employee satisfaction, and loss of workers. Such policies promote career growth opportunities and reduce the negative effects of the role conflict, especially for working women. Furthermore, moms frequently gain new skills, such as time management and problem-solving, which benefit their work. However, progress towards attaining gender equality in the workplace is still hampered by the presence of structural and cultural obstacles like the glass ceiling and the “ideal worker” stereotype.

Additionally, governments play a vital role in creating work conditions that allow individuals to successfully manage their personal and professional lives. According to the global rankings of WLB practices, policies including statutory leave, healthcare benefits, and flexible work schedules have been successful in several nations. Interestingly, New Zealand’s extensive work-life balance legislation has set the standard, illustrating the real advantages of a government-supported strategy for striking a balance between work and personal life.

Limitations and Future Research

Regardless of the positive findings, this study had a few limitations. Most of the study is focused on qualitative assessments, and the sample size of the examined studies is somewhat small. To give a more thorough understanding of WLB, future research should try to incorporate a wider range of literature and use a variety of approaches. It would be especially beneficial to conduct longitudinal research to examine how WLB interventions affect employee well-being and organizational success in the long term. Additionally, studies examining how gender, socioeconomic status, and cultural factors influence WLB experiences can provide a more profound understanding of the diverse needs of the workforce.

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Information about the author

- Altina Avdullahi, MA Student of HR Counselling. ELTE University, Budapest, Hungary. E-mail: altinaavdullahi@gmail.com